

Report for Multiplier Event

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Multiplier Event ID: 3

Organizing team: dr. Gintarė Tautkevičienė, Aistė Pranckutė, Daiva Didžgalvienė, Kaunas University of Technology Library

Title: Strengthening the Role of Libraries for Rising Citizen Science: LibOCS shares knowledge and experience

Type: Face-to-face

Date: 11/06/2024

Venue: Kaunas University of Technology Campus Library (Studentų St. 48, Kaunas, Lithuania)

For more than two years, partners of the Erasmus+ project "University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through citizen science in the Baltics (LibOCS)" have been conducting activities to strengthen citizen science in the Baltic region. On 11/06/2024 the 3rd Multiplier Event (ME3) took place at Kaunas University of Technology Campus Library (Studentų St. 48, Kaunas, Lithuania). The event was organized by Kaunas University of Technology team. The objectives of the event were:

- To present the project results and connect to relevant stakeholders in the country (Librarians from academic and public libraries, and other stakeholders interested in CS)
- To increase sustainability of results through their uptake by participating stakeholders.

25 librarians from academic libraries, Kaunas Municipal Vincas Kudirka Public Library and Kaunas Ažuolynas library took part in the event. In addition, 16 project partners from Tartu University, TalTECH, University of Latvia, Vytautas Magnus University, Immer Besser and Web2Learn joined the event.

KTU Library Director Dr. Gintare Tautkeviciene welcomed the participants and moderated the event. Project coordinator Liisi Lembinen presented the LibOCS project overall. Tartu University team with Svea Kaseorg and Lilian Neerut shared the PR1 results with deeper insights on the main drivers and barriers for libraries in citizen science. Gita Rozenberga presented the results of two surveys that revealed the attitudes of researchers, researchers' attitudes towards citizen science and citizen science practitioners' attitudes towards libraries memory institutions' inclusion into citizen science projects. Aistė Pranckutė, KTU

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competencies librarians need to be involved in citizen science projects and how these competencies can be developed. The open-access self-paced learning course "Citizen Science for Librarians" attracted the interest of librarians. No less interesting was the presentation by Dr. Tiberius Ignat from Immer Besser on BESPOC, Citizen Science Single Point of Contact prototype and its implementation in Higher Education institutions. The TalTECH Library team, Kaarin Birk and Tuuliki Toiste presented the Toolkit for Librarians on Citizen Science. Last but not least, the presentation from Assoc. Prof. Dr. Aldona Augustiniene, the guest speaker from Kaunas University of Technology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities was given to the participants. Her topic was „How to communicate science to society? Storytelling for Citizen Science“ and the audience not only had a great theoretical background and some examples but also were involved in some practical exercises.

Feedback on the content of the event and its relevance to the target audience was collected orally (during the event) and in writing (after the event). Immediately after the event, participants shared their impressions and insights on the presentations they had heard, and discussed whether the information could be useful in their daily activities. The feedback was positive. The topic of citizen science was of particular interest to the representatives of public libraries, who were pleased to have had the opportunity to access the citizen science toolkit and the self-learning course.

After the event, a post-event survey with 6 questions was sent to all participants by email. 15 respondents completed the questionnaire. The survey asked participants to rate how the event met their expectations, which presentations were most interesting and useful, what they liked most about the event and what they would suggest improving. They were also asked if they would like to participate in similar events in the future. In summary, the event met the expectations of the vast majority of participants (93.3% of respondents). The content of the presentations was very well received, with all presentations rated as good or very good. Only 13% of those who responded were not sure whether they would attend a similar event in the future, while 87% assured that they would be interested in such events in the future. When asked what they liked most about the event, respondents noted the good organisation and pleasant atmosphere of the event, and the informative and practical presentations. In response to the question on what could be improved, a suggestion was made to choose more audience-engaging tools. The comments made will be taken into consideration when organising similar events in the future.

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